

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

Deliverable D5.1 Principles for Capacity Building

HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-ECCCH-01

Horizon Innovation action

Responsible author: Toma Tasovac (DARIAH)

Project start	1 June 2024
Project duration	60 months
Document Identifier	10.5281/zenodo.17513834

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

ECHOES is a project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement n.101157364, with the support of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee n.10110142 & n.10110466.

© 2025 by the authors, the ECHOES consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

Deliverable Information

Project Number	101157364	Acronym	ECHOES
Full title	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science		
Project URL	https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/		
EU Project Officer	Christian WILK		

Deliverable	D5.1	Title	Principles for Capacity Building
Work Package	WP5	Title	Capacity Building and Training
Submission date	29/11/2024		
Pages	28	Keywords	Capacity building, Training, Communities

Lead Partner	DARIAH
Responsible Author	Toma Tasovac (DARIAH)
Authors (Partner)	Toma Tasovac (DARIAH), Sebastiaan ter Burg (EUROPEANA), Elis Marçal (E.C.C.O), Elisabeth Stadlinger (ONB)
Contributors	Carlos Andujar (UPC), Julia Fallon (EUROPEANA), Charlotte Gallini (FSP), Andreas Georgopoulos (ICOMOS), Mira Höschler (NEMO), Sandie Le Conte (INP), Faye Nzegang (ICOMOS), Rémi Petitcol (FSP), Julian Richards (UoY-ADS; ARIADNE RI), Alejandro Ríos (UPC), Amalia Siatou (E.C.C.O.)

Change log

Date	Version	Author	Change
29/11/2025	V1.0	Tasovac et al.	Final draft
29/11/2024	V1.0	Mailane Sampaio (CNRS)	Editing
29/11/2024	V1.0	Xavier Rodier (CNRS)	Proofreading

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Abstract

The overarching goal of this document is to provide common, high-level guidelines for developing impactful capacity-building resources within the ECHOES project. Key challenges in the cultural heritage sector, such as limited resources, fragmentation, technical knowledge gaps, and barriers to communication and data sharing, underscore the need for a cohesive and strategic approach to capacity building.

Highlights from the document:

- Strategic Context and Collaborative Insights
 - Fragmented priorities and siloed practices in the sector limit knowledge sharing and innovation.
 - The absence of standard, sector-wide digital maturity frameworks complicates self-assessment, goal setting, and prioritizing resource allocation.
 - Tailored capacity-building initiatives and collaborative strategies are necessary to address diverse professional groups, different types of heritage assets, and varying levels of digital expertise.
 - Clear documentation, glossaries, cross-disciplinary training opportunities as well as a proactive approach to linguistic diversity are a sine qua non to fostering effective communication and collaboration across the sector.
 - It is essential that digital literacy and a commitment to lifelong learning become recognized as key assets for career advancement.
 - Data-sharing platforms must prioritise strong security protocols and provide clear, standardised licensing frameworks that protect ownership while enabling ethical reuse.
- Principles
 - Focus on People: Prioritize people by aligning training with learners' needs, fostering professional networks, and driving both personal and community development.
 - Strive for Excellence: High-quality training requires rigorous standards, skilled trainers, and formal recognition of achievements to motivate learners and maintain impact.
 - Foster Openness and Accessibility: Promote FAIR-by-design training resources with open licensing and adherence to accessibility standards.
 - Promote Inclusion and Diversity: Capacity-building measures must cater to a diverse range of professionals from diverse backgrounds and with diverse abilities.

- Ensure Sustainability: Training initiatives need long-term planning, continuous updates, and systematic integration of user feedback to foster trust and ongoing engagement with the resources.
- Provide Flexibility and Adaptability: Capacity-building measures should offer modular learning pathways and adaptable content to meet diverse learner needs and reflect local contexts.
- Stay Relevant and Impact-Driven: Focus on practical, actionable outcomes that keep up the pace with technological developments and emerging legal frameworks to ensure long-term relevance and effectiveness.
- Paths to implementation
 - Capacity-building principles should be embedded into the strategic planning, workflows, and collaborations within the ECHOES project and the Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage as a whole.
 - Project partners should foster a learning-centric culture, encouraging life-long learning and creating opportunities for reflective practices, enabling participants to assess and share how they apply their new skills.
 - Project partners should adhere to the principles or provide justifications for exceptions, ensuring transparency in addressing constraints such as accessibility or format.
 - Strengthening partnerships and networks through co-developing open-access resources, co-hosting events, and creating mentorship and peer-learning opportunities fosters collective growth.
 - Establishing metrics to assess success (e.g., learner satisfaction, skill application, and community impact) is a precondition for continuous refinement and improvement.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	6
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	6
1.2 Structure of the Document	7
2. Challenges in the Cultural Heritage Sector	8
2.1 Limited Resources	8
2.2 Fragmentation	9
2.3 Obstacles to communication and collaboration	10
2.4 Technical and Knowledge Gaps	12
2.5 Data Sharing, Intellectual Property and Questions of Trust	13
3. The Landscape of Capacity Building in ECHOES	16
3.1 Tailored Approaches	16
3.2 Collaboration and Partnerships	17
3.3 Continuous Professional Development	19
3.4 Measuring Impact and Effectiveness	19
3.5 Conclusion	20
4. Principles for Capacity Building	21
4.1 Principle 1: Focus on People	22
4.2 Principle 2: Strive for Excellence	22
4.3 Principle 3: Foster Openness and Accessibility	23
4.4 Principle 4: Promote Inclusion and Diversity	23
4.5 Principle 5: Ensure Sustainability	23
4.6 Principle 6: Provide Flexibility and Adaptability	24
4.7 Principle 7: Stay Relevant and Impact-Driven	24
5. Conclusion	25
5.1 Relation to Other Tasks and Work Packages	25
5.2 Paths to Implementation	25
References	27

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The overarching goal of this document is to provide common, high-level **guidelines for developing impactful capacity-building resources within the ECHOES project**. To achieve that goal, the document delineates a set of foundational principles that:

- **represent core values** embedded in the mission and vision of capacity building within ECHOES;
- **promote community engagement** from all stakeholders, including cultural heritage institutions and professionals, researchers, as well as the general public; and
- ensure that all capacity-building initiatives and resources developed within the project remain **sustainable** and **accessible to diverse audiences** across Europe and beyond.

Training generally refers to the process in which individuals or groups gain specific skills or knowledge needed to perform particular tasks. Training is often short-term and focused on specific goals, such as learning how to use a software tool, understanding a protocol, or developing a particular technical skill. **Capacity building**, on the other hand, is a broader, long-term process that aims to generally enhance the capabilities and resources of individuals, organisations, or communities. It encompasses training but also includes other methods, like mentorship, resource development and allocation, enhancement of human resources, networking and lobbying. In other words, training should be understood as a tool or component within the broader strategy of capacity building. **Capacity building focuses on the holistic development of skills, knowledge, and resources necessary to ensure ongoing growth and improvement.**

ECHOES' overall mission is to set up the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), a shared platform designed to facilitate collaboration among cultural heritage professionals and researchers, enabling them to modernise their workflows and processes. This platform will offer access to data, cutting-edge scientific and training resources, and advanced digital tools, all developed collaboratively by the heritage community to meet their specific requirements.

It goes without saying that **training and capacity building are essential** for the success of such an ambitious enterprise. ECHOES plans to integrate the currently fragmented communities within the cultural heritage (CH) sector and bring together diverse actors from various fields and disciplines into a **cohesive community** focused on the Digital

Commons. A successful collaboration among **institutions of varying sizes and capabilities** will to a large extent depend on a **meaningful and coherent capacity building strategy** so that all future users of the Collaborative Cloud, regardless of their technical background, have the skills necessary to fully engage with and benefit from it.

Drawing on the challenges facing the cultural heritage sector and the expertise and experience of ECHOES partners, the principles presented here serve as a strategic foundation for helping the development and dissemination of knowledge in the ECCCH. The aim is to foster collaboration across national and institutional boundaries, and, ultimately, build a more resilient and connected cultural heritage sector in Europe. By establishing a common approach to capacity building, the ECHOES project should be able to maximise its impact and, in the longer term, offer a substantial contribution to making CH more accessible, engaging, and sustainable for future generations.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The document is organised into five chapters. This introductory chapter defines the purpose and the scope of the document. Chapter 2 explores key challenges which the cultural heritage sector must address to achieve digital maturity. Chapter 3 highlights existing frameworks and key experiences from project partners that offer insight into effective strategies for fostering digital readiness and professional development. Chapter 4 presents seven high-level principles to guide the development of effective, inclusive, and sustainable capacity-building measures. Finally, Chapter 5 contextualizes these principles in relation to other tasks in the project, and offers recommendations about possible paths to implementation.

2. Challenges in the Cultural Heritage Sector

2.1 Limited Resources

Many cultural heritage (CH) institutions, especially smaller galleries, libraries, archives and museums operate with **limited financial and human resources**. The same can be said of private enterprises and community initiatives that are involved in various aspects of heritage activities including, for instance, conservation-restoration practices, cultural mediation, audience development etc. This scarcity affects their ability to:

- invest in necessary technologies for digitisation and preservation, and recruit the professionals with an expertise in digitisation;
- provide adequate training and professional development; and
- maintain and update infrastructure to meet modern preservation standards.

The lack of resources can lead to inadequate preservation practices, reduced accessibility of collections, and an inability to adopt innovative technologies that could enhance engagement with cultural heritage (see UNESCO 2015).

Compounding the resource limitations faced by many cultural heritage institutions, private enterprises and community initiatives is the **lack of sector-wide digital maturity ambitions and assessment tools**. Institutions and their leaders often struggle to define clear digital goals or understand what specific milestones they should be aiming for. This ambiguity makes it difficult for them to define concrete digital goals or evaluate their progress in terms of digital maturity. Without a shared vision or a well-established framework, these stakeholders are left to navigate the digital landscape in isolation, relying on their own internal priorities and interpretations, which may not align with broader sectoral needs.

Even though there are many organisations offering support, services or tools to create a digital maturity index (see, for example, McNab 2021; and Finnis and Kennedy 2022), the **absence of standardised industry benchmarks in cultural heritage** remains a sore point. In other sectors, benchmarks and maturity models often provide stakeholders with a roadmap for digital development, offering clear stages of progression and measurable targets. However, in the cultural heritage field, no such widely accepted models exist. This means institutions are unsure of when they have taken appropriate steps or reached a level of digital proficiency that aligns with current technological trends and sectoral expectations. The lack of these benchmarks also prevents institutions from conducting meaningful self-assessments or making informed

comparisons with peers, which could otherwise serve as motivation or provide useful insights into how to enhance their own strategies.

This uncertainty complicates efforts to prioritise resource allocation effectively. Without a clear understanding of where they stand or what they should be aiming for, institutions may **struggle to justify investments in new technologies, infrastructure, or staff training**. A related challenge is deciding whom to upskill: focus on training one key individual who can become a digital leader, or aim for minimum digital literacy across all staff members? If the leadership of an institution lacks digital awareness, how shall the institution develop a digital strategy that makes sense? As a result of these kinds of dilemmas, institutions may either underinvest, failing to keep pace with technological advancements, or overinvest in areas that do not align with their long-term goals or sector-wide trends. Furthermore, the inability to assess progress at both the institutional and sector-wide levels hinders the development of coordinated strategies and collaborative initiatives. In a sector where resources are already stretched, this lack of direction can slow the overall pace of digital innovation and hinder the adoption of new technologies, ultimately limiting the sector's ability to preserve, share, and engage with cultural heritage in dynamic and sustainable ways.

2.2 Fragmentation

Although the term “Cultural Heritage” may imply a well-defined and cohesive concept, in reality, it encompasses an **extensive and highly diverse range of both tangible and intangible assets**. This diversity reflects the **wide array of professional fields and individuals** engaged in cultural heritage work, which range from archivists, librarians, museum curators and conservation experts, on the one hand, to historians, archaeologists, cultural mediators, educators and digital humanists, on the other. Each group interacts with cultural heritage from different perspectives, with distinct methodologies, goals, and professional needs. As a result, the sector's multifaceted nature can often lead to complex and diverse solutions in capacity building, requiring tailored solutions to achieve the desired collaboration and unlock its capacity for innovation.

This fragmentation poses a significant challenge because the varied needs and priorities of different groups within the cultural heritage sector can impede efforts to unify around common digital transformation goals. For instance, the tools and training required by the professionals focusing on the digital preservation of ancient manuscripts may differ drastically from those working with intangible heritage like oral traditions. Without careful coordination, these divergent needs can prevent the sharing of knowledge,

resources, and digital methodologies, creating silos that limit the sector's overall capacity to innovate.

Rather than strengthening the sector's collective skills and capabilities, this fragmentation can slow down the adoption of new digital technologies and methodologies. CH institutions and professionals with specialised needs may struggle to see the relevance or benefit of sector-wide initiatives, such as digital repositories, cloud-based collaboration platforms, or AI-driven data analysis tools. At the same time, the lack of shared understanding and collaboration opportunities can hinder the sector's ability to pool resources, share best practices, and develop comprehensive strategies that work across different fields of cultural heritage.

Addressing this challenge to capacity-building requires a multifaceted approach that recognizes the inherent plurality of the cultural heritage sector. **A one-size-fits-all solution is unlikely to succeed.** Instead, the sector needs a broad spectrum of capacity-building and training initiatives tailored to different professional groups, heritage types, and digital expertise levels. This could include specialised training for digital archiving, 3D modelling for CH objects, or AI-enhanced metadata generation, alongside more general digital literacy programs for those just beginning their digital transformation journey.

2.3 Obstacles to communication and collaboration

One of the most significant challenges in the cultural heritage (CH) sector is fostering effective communication and collaboration among diverse stakeholders, particularly in large-scale, complex projects like ECHOES and, by extension, the ECCCH. These initiatives involve a wide range of participants, including CH professionals, technical experts, humanists, heritage scientists, and institutional leaders, each with their own perspectives, expertise, and levels of familiarity with the technologies and methodologies involved. This diversity can be both a strength and a challenge, as it brings a wealth of knowledge to the table but also creates barriers to clear communication and shared understanding.

A key issue in such collaborative efforts is the **varied levels of familiarity with cutting-edge concepts and technologies.** For many stakeholders, particularly those less experienced with digital infrastructures, the added value of cloud-based solutions can be difficult to grasp. Questions such as "What is the practical benefit of using the cloud for cultural heritage?" or "How does participating in a project like this create value for my institution?" or "How does the Cloud improve and facilitate my daily professional practice?" are common. Explaining these benefits to a wide audience—ranging from seasoned technologists to CH professionals who may be less familiar with digital

methodologies—requires tailored communication strategies. Without clear, accessible explanations, some stakeholders may find it hard to justify their involvement or fully engage with the project’s goals, potentially slowing down collaboration and project progress.

Another major obstacle is the **significant differences in vocabulary and communication styles across the sectors involved**. Cultural heritage professionals, technical experts, heritage scientists and humanists often use different terminologies, even when discussing the same concepts. For instance, a term as seemingly straightforward as “data quality” may have vastly different meanings depending on the context. For a data scientist, it might refer to the completeness, consistency, and accuracy of a dataset, while a CH professional might focus on the questions of provenance, accuracy of source used, rigour of the information provided or contextual integrity of digitised heritage objects. These differences in interpretation can lead to misunderstandings and hinder collaboration, as participants may not always realise they are talking past one another.

This terminological divide underscores the need for a shared language or clearer communication frameworks within collaborative digital heritage projects. Establishing common definitions and ensuring that all participants have a baseline understanding of key concepts can help bridge these gaps. Clear **documentation, glossaries, and cross-disciplinary training** can play a crucial role in aligning perspectives and promoting smoother communication within and across sectors.

Multilingualism also presents a significant challenge in international CH projects. Many institutions and projects are limited by the ability to work in only one or two languages, which restricts access for non-native speakers. CH practices cover a diverse range of highly specialised fields and professions, with very technical and scientific concepts and terms. This language barrier can hinder not only participation in discussions and decision-making processes but also the accurate translation of project resources, training materials, and documentation. In complex, technical projects like ECCCH, where precision and clarity are critical, language barriers can lead to misinterpretation and errors in implementation.

Ensuring inclusivity in communication requires a more **proactive approach to language diversity**. This might involve translating key materials into multiple languages, providing language support during meetings and training sessions, and fostering an environment where non-native speakers feel comfortable contributing. By addressing these language barriers, projects can broaden participation and ensure that stakeholders from different linguistic backgrounds can fully engage with the initiative.

2.4 Technical and Knowledge Gaps

The CH sector is composed of a **broad spectrum of professionals with varying levels of technical and digital proficiency**. On one end of the spectrum are experts who regularly use advanced tools and methods like spectroscopic analysis or 3D modelling (e.g., Sketchfab) and those who manage large-scale digitization projects. On the other end, there are those who may be more familiar with traditional heritage management practices but lack experience with digital tools. This variation creates significant challenges in implementing digital initiatives and projects that require collaboration across teams with different areas of expertise.

For example, while 3D modelling experts may easily engage with tools for creating and manipulating digital replicas of heritage objects, CH professionals who are less digitally experienced may struggle to understand the full potential of these technologies or how to integrate them into their workflows, and daily practice. At the same time, however, 3D modelling experts may not always fully understand the potential impact of the decisions they make during the modelling process. While a 3D model might appear visually impressive, it may fail to accurately represent the original object in critical aspects such as scale, materials, colours, or structure. This can risk creating future misinterpretations and diminishing the integrity of the original piece. To address these kinds of disparities in skills, experiences and perspectives, we need tailored training and support systems that cater to different levels of expertise. Without this support, the gap between digital experts and less-experienced users will continue to widen, impacting the overall digital transformation of the sector.

Furthermore, as the CH sector increasingly engages with cutting-edge digital technologies, new challenges emerge around the use and understanding of advanced data structures and models, such as complex ontologies, knowledge graphs, and heritage digital twins. These technologies offer powerful tools for representing, organising, and interpreting CH data, but they can also be highly abstract and difficult to grasp, even for seasoned professionals within the field.

For some CH professionals, these advanced topics can feel overwhelming and difficult to relate to their day-to-day work. The concepts of ontologies and digital twins may appear distant and abstract, making it challenging for these professionals to fully engage with or contribute to digital projects that rely on these technologies. Bridging this gap between developers, who create and manage these tools, and CH professionals, who provide the content and context, will be crucial for the success of projects such as ECHOES.

This challenge calls for more than just training in computational methods—it requires fostering transdisciplinary collaboration and communication. Developers must work closely with CH professionals to ensure that the tools being created are both user-friendly and aligned with the needs of the sector. Similarly, CH professionals must be supported in understanding the potential benefits of these technologies and how they can be integrated into heritage management and preservation practices. **It is essential that digital literacy and a commitment to lifelong learning become recognized as key assets for career advancement.** Training opportunities must be seen as beneficial not just at the individual level, but also institutionally, allowing participants to valorise the new skills in their careers. Valorisation should be embedded in institutional frameworks, whereby completing digital training programs is acknowledged and recognised as a step toward professional growth and higher roles within the organisation.

2.5 Data Sharing, Intellectual Property and Questions of Trust

Data sharing has become a cornerstone of digital transformation in the cultural heritage (CH) sector, offering immense potential for collaboration, innovation, and accessibility. Despite these benefits, however, many stakeholders remain hesitant to share their data, driven by **concerns over security, licensing, ownership, and the potential misuse of sensitive or valuable information.** These ethical and legal issues create significant barriers to participation in digital platforms and initiatives like the ECCCH, limiting their effectiveness and preventing the full realisation of their potential as trusted resources for the sector.

The heritage sector is fundamentally shaped by **legal frameworks** that **define actions, responsibilities, and freedoms concerning heritage resources.** Governance in this field is not an EU-level competence but falls under the principle of subsidiarity. This means that policies, legal and administrative procedures, and systems for protection, listing, and inventorying heritage resources are the responsibility of individual countries, **implemented at the national, regional, or even local levels,** depending on the governance structures that are in place. Furthermore, heritage protection and professional practices are influenced by international charters, conventions, and principles, which are subsequently integrated into national laws and professional codes of conduct. This results in a **diverse array of regulatory frameworks and guiding principles shaped by multilevel policies.** A notable example is the variation in national **copyright laws** and legal restrictions on sharing heritage-related data, which remain prevalent across most, if not all, EU countries. Another challenge is the **differentiation between CH data legal frameworks and research data legal frameworks,** which is

particularly relevant for ECHOES as most data used within the Collaborative Cloud will effectively be both. Additionally, regulations such as the EU's **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** create another layer of complexity, particularly when handling **personal data** linked to heritage resources or projects involving public participation. For instance, GDPR requires explicit consent for the collection and use of personal data in citizen science initiatives or crowd-sourced heritage documentation projects.

Data sharing is sometimes hindered by **challenges related to outsourcing digitisation activities to commercial companies**. Key issues include **restrictive licences, exclusive access agreements, access fees** and **data sovereignty concerns**, all of which can limit public or scholarly access to and reuse of the data. In some cases, **unclear or overlapping intellectual property rights** discourage institutions and heritage professionals from sharing data out of fear of violating legal restrictions or losing control over their assets. Moreover, institutions may worry that releasing high-quality digital versions of cultural objects will diminish their value or that the data could be reused in ways that they cannot control, such as in commercial projects or without proper attribution.

These concerns are especially pronounced in an era where advanced technologies, like **AI and machine learning**, are increasingly being used to analyse and manipulate digital heritage data. The fear of how such data might be repurposed without adequate oversight, quality assurance, integrity safeguards or ethical guidelines exacerbates reluctance to share. To overcome these challenges, data-sharing platforms must prioritise **strong security protocols** and provide **clear, standardised licensing frameworks that protect ownership while enabling reuse**.

Establishing trust in data-sharing platforms and cloud infrastructures is critical to encouraging participation from the CH sector. Currently, in some institutions there is a gap in trust between the perceived risks of sharing data and the potential benefits of doing so. To gain widespread adoption, platforms like ECCCH must address these trust issues head-on by offering robust data protection measures, transparency about how data is created and used, and assurances that institutions will retain control over their contributions.

Furthermore, fostering trust requires clear communication about the security measures in place, such as **encryption, access control, and monitoring of data use**. Institutions need assurances that the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage will be able to handle massive quantities of complex data responsibly and ethically while safeguarding against unauthorized access or misuse. Providing institutions with flexible options for sharing—such as defining different levels of access or use restrictions—can also help mitigate concerns by giving them greater control over how their data is used.

Efforts should also be made to highlight the **impact and benefits of data reuse, such as increased visibility, enhanced collaboration, production of new knowledge and the potential for new research discoveries**. Ensuring that institutions understand the long-term value of sharing data, both for their own organisational goals and for the wider CH community, is key to fostering a positive attitude towards data-sharing platforms.

Encouraging greater participation in data-sharing platforms also requires addressing the motivations of institutions and CH professionals, especially those supplying valuable data. Institutions are often driven by the **potential for reputational gains and organisational benefits, such as increased visibility, collaborative opportunities, or enhanced research capabilities**. Recognising these motivations and aligning them with the goals of the platform is critical for fostering sustained engagement over time.

2.6 Conclusion

Addressing the challenges outlined in this chapter requires coordinated, comprehensive capacity-building efforts across the CH sector. By adhering to common principles, such as those proposed in the next chapter, institutions can work together to bridge gaps in resources, skills, and infrastructure, ensuring that cultural heritage is both preserved and made accessible to diverse audiences across Europe. Creating an inclusive, interoperable, and resilient framework for the management and dissemination of cultural heritage will not only safeguard the digital future of these assets but also enhance public engagement and understanding of Europe's rich and diverse cultural legacy.

3. The Landscape of Capacity Building in ECHOES

Capacity building is an essential priority for the cultural heritage (CH) sector as it grapples with growing pressures to adopt digital technologies, respond to the challenges of digital preservation, and engage with increasingly diverse audiences through innovative approaches to digital engagement. The evolving digital landscape, coupled with the sector's inherently multidisciplinary nature, has led to the development of various frameworks and approaches aimed at strengthening institutional capabilities and enhancing individual skills. This chapter outlines the current landscape of capacity building from the point of view of the ECHOES consortium, highlighting existing frameworks and key experiences from project partners that offer insight into effective strategies for fostering digital readiness and professional development.

It would be beyond the scope of this deliverable to make a truly representative industry-wide overview of capacity building in Europe. Yet because of the diversity of the ECHOES consortium, we can draw upon a broad spectrum of experiences and insights that collectively reflect key trends and common practices in capacity building across the European CH sector.

3.1 Tailored Approaches

Effective capacity building requires tailored approaches that consider the specific needs and contexts of different communities both in terms of cultural and disciplinary specificities. ECHOES partners have a great deal of experience designing programs to be inclusive, empowering local members and early-career professionals to take on leadership roles.

By fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders—ranging from individual researchers to large institutions—DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) emphasises the importance of context-specific solutions that address the unique challenges and needs of different communities. A key element of this effort is [DARIAH-Campus](#), a hosting platform and discovery framework for open educational resources, designed to meet the specific needs of arts and humanities researchers. Training and education are essential for ensuring the social sustainability of research and data infrastructures because they provide users with the necessary skills to engage effectively with infrastructural tools and services. Complementing this, DARIAH's position paper on [Cultural Heritage Data from a Humanities Research Perspective](#) (Tasovac et al. 2020) underscores the critical role of CH data in driving humanities research. DARIAH advocates for the recognition of heritage datasets as fundamental

research outputs, highlighting the need for infrastructures and skilled users that support their preservation, interoperability, and reuse.

The European Research Infrastructure of Heritage Science (E-RIHS) delivers integrated access to a wide range of instrumentation, data, expertise, and technologies applied to Cultural Heritage. In order to train its community of users and partners in new scientific methods applied to CH, or train researchers on heritage-related topics and practices, it has launched [Heritage Science \(HS\) Academy](#). It offers a wide range of training opportunities focusing on the study of CH objects, such as lectures, webinars, meetings, training camps, summer schools and workshops. The HS Academy is designed to complement academic or vocational training by bringing together the best practices in education from STEMs, Social Sciences and Humanities, and cultural heritage vocational training. Its annual capacity-building offer is decided by an editorial committee composed of confirmed researchers and professionals as well as early-stage researchers and users.

Europeana has invested in both formal and informal capacity-building initiatives. The formal capacity building mostly encompasses the directly controllable types of capacity building, such as organisational development of the sector and institutions and the development and delivery of training. Both these activities are based on research and input given by many cultural heritage professionals from the [Europeana Network Association](#) (ENA). The components and supporting services and tools of Europeana's training activities are gathered in the [Europeana Capacity Building Framework](#). A few practical examples are the [Europeana Academy](#), through which self-paced courses are offered and instructor-led training that complements these self-paced resources. The [Guidelines for training development and delivery](#) have been developed and are used for each course to ensure coherent user experiences and quality levels of the training resources. On the other hand, informal capacity building by the Europeana Foundation is done through its [events](#), advocacy work, supporting the Europeana Network Association and activities for European Member States.

3.2 Collaboration and Partnerships

Building strong partnerships and networks is crucial for sharing knowledge and resources. Collaborations between universities, research institutions, international organisations, and industry partners can enhance the reach and impact of capacity-building initiatives.

International non-governmental organisations like the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS) play a vital role in capacity building through cultural heritage documentation and the facilitation of training measures. The extensive

resources available on the ICOMOS website, including charters, [doctrinal texts](#), and [publications](#), offer valuable insights that can be reviewed and integrated into ECHOES tasks. As an association, ICOMOS brings together over 11,000 cultural heritage professionals in more than 130 countries. Through its National Committees, its International Scientific Committees and its Working Groups, ICOMOS is a network of experts that benefits from the interdisciplinary exchange of its members. The ICOMOS University Forum and [CIPA Heritage Documentation](#), which offers summer schools and encourages the development of tools and practices for the recording, documentation and information management for all aspects of cultural heritage, highlight the organisation's commitment to education and capacity building.

Engaging with universities that transmit knowledge and skills related to cultural heritage or any academic domain that can be applied to cultural heritage, such as those, for instance, that form the [Una Europa](#) alliance, can provide insights into effective educational strategies and curricula. ECHOES will benefit from the collective experience of universities or other higher education institutions that participate in the project, covering diverse fields such as computer science, engineering, physics, chemistry, art history, history, and heritage conservation. Their contribution will ensure good articulation between ECHOES capacity-building principles and activities and the academic training of the next generations of professionals.

In the archaeological sector, the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) has made effective use of COST Actions to support capacity building for FAIR data provision amongst European national heritage organisations and museums. The [SEADDA](#) COST Action (Saving European Archaeology from a Digital Dark Age) ran alongside the ARIADNEPlus project from 2019-23. The aim was to mitigate the loss of primary archaeological data by developing common understandings around data stewardship, building new best-practice networks to support the preservation and open dissemination of archaeological data, and the creation of more inclusive research partnerships. It increased international awareness about the risks to the digital archaeological record and produced 45 peer-reviewed, open-access publications, providing a sustainable outlet for ongoing progress through the establishment of the ARIADNE Research Infrastructure (see, for instance, Richards et al. 2021).

In the library sector, the concept of [Library Labs](#) has emerged as a significant capacity-building component within digital libraries. These labs provide not only data access but also training infrastructure, including tutorials, tools, and metadata information. They cater to different knowledge levels, making them suitable for both inexperienced and experienced users, as well as for professional and private use cases. By reaching out to

external data repositories and publishing source code on shared platforms like GitHub, Library Labs foster an environment of open collaboration and innovation.

3.3 Continuous Professional Development

Supporting continuous professional development is essential in a sector characterised by rapid technological changes. Projects like BIBLIO and Mu.SA have been instrumental in addressing the digital skills gap in specific CH sectors.

BIBLIO (Boosting digital skills and competencies for librarians in Europe) focused on boosting digital skills and competencies for librarians in Europe, analysing the library sector to highlight skills gaps and support librarians in gaining new skills and developing innovative services. It creates a digital ecosystem for skills assessment, learning offers, validation, and recognition, moving beyond a simple e-learning platform.

The **Mu.SA** (Museum Sector Alliance) project, with NEMO as a partner, aimed to tackle the disconnection between formal education and the evolving requirements of the museum sector due to digital transformation. It addresses the shortage of digital and transferable skills by supporting the continuous professional development of museum professionals. Both projects underscore the necessity of targeted initiatives to equip CH professionals with the competencies required in a rapidly changing digital landscape.

NEMO's ongoing capacity-building programs, including trainings and webinars, have played an important role in supporting museum professionals. **NEMO** is committed to fostering learning exchanges and providing training opportunities at all professional levels through various activities conducted on a European scale. Every NEMO member is encouraged to participate in the **Working Group Digital Transformation**, which offers opportunities to exchange knowledge and explore topics related to digital advancements in museums. This working group empowers European museums to harness the full potential of digitalisation by addressing new processes, tasks, and challenges.

3.4 Measuring Impact and Effectiveness

One of the common challenges in capacity building is assessing the impact of training and development initiatives. Organisations like Europeana have developed specific frameworks to tackle this issue. The Europeana Impact Framework and the accompanying **Impact Playbook** provide structured approaches to evaluate the outcomes of capacity-building activities. These tools help organisations understand not only the immediate effects but also the long-term benefits and areas for improvement.

3.5 Conclusion

The landscape of capacity building in cultural heritage is dynamic and multifaceted, reflecting the sector's ongoing digital transformation and the diverse needs of its professionals. By embracing multiform training opportunities, leveraging collaborative networks, addressing digital skills gaps, and integrating existing principles and frameworks, members of the ECHOES consortium have a history of innovating and adapting their approaches to ensure that their capacity-building efforts are both effective and sustainable – despite the numerous challenges, which we outlined in the previous chapter.

Strategies that focus on tailored approaches, inclusivity, collaboration, and continuous professional development offer promising paths forward. The collective experiences of the ECHOES consortium as a whole, and insights from various organisations and projects that our consortium members have been part of, underscore the importance of a cohesive and coordinated effort in capacity building, ultimately contributing to the resilience and vitality of the cultural heritage sector.

4. Principles for Capacity Building

The Capacity Building Principles described in this chapter provide a set of common, high-level recommendations for developing effective, inclusive, and sustainable capacity-building resources within the ECHOES project. The ECHOES principles embody commitments to core values that inform the design, delivery, and evaluation of our capacity-building initiatives. They emphasise the importance of adaptability, fitness-for-purpose, quality, and human-centred design, ensuring that capacity-building efforts meet the diverse needs of the sector while fostering long-term growth and resilience.

Operating in the domain of cultural heritage inherently involves a unique set of social responsibilities and challenges. The democratisation of heritage, its increasing recognition as a key factor for sustainable development, its fundamental role in the construction of the sense of cultural identity and social cohesion, and its contributions to innovation create profound expectations for those working in the field. In response, members of the ECHOES consortium acknowledge a foundational set of CH-specific principles introduced by the CHARTER Consortium to guide professional actions in this value-driven, socially meaningful environment. These include:

- **Recognising heritage in context.** Capacity-building efforts should cultivate an awareness of heritage within diverse and dynamic cultural landscapes, encouraging individuals to appreciate heritage both in their environment and in broader contexts.
- **Respecting heritage as a common good.** Effective training must instil an understanding of heritage as a collective resource, emphasizing shared responsibilities among various stakeholders.
- **Appreciating diverse perspectives.** Acknowledging and addressing evolving and sometimes conflicting views on heritage ensures inclusive and meaningful engagement.
- **Engaging with diverse stakeholders.** Professionals must be equipped to work effectively with a diverse range of stakeholders, fostering cooperation and mutual understanding both within and across sectors.
- **Mitigating risks.** Capacity-building measures must include strategies for safeguarding heritage against risks such as neglect, misuse, and external threats (see Corr et al., 2023 p 53-4)

The capacity-building activities undertaken by the ECHOES project should also take into account the foundational principles and commitments made by public service institutions engaged in cultural heritage training and education such as the *Institut national du patrimoine*. These include the recognition of the need for **sustainable**

development, promotion of professional diversity and equality, artistic and cultural education, attention to students and people with special needs, and public service missions.

By respecting these foundational commitments, the ECHOES project will aim to deliver capacity-building resources that not only enhance professional capabilities in the digital domain, which is the main goal of the project, but also reflect the broader societal value of cultural heritage. The following principles, which have been developed through extensive consultations within the consortium, will serve as a framework for developing an actionable strategy that will translate foundational commitments into practical outcomes.

4.1 Principle 1: Focus on People

At its core, capacity building is about people. Capacity-building programs should measure their success not only by the technical skills imparted but also by their tangible impact on individuals and communities. By establishing and implementing clear learning outcomes, providers can ensure that training is aligned with the needs of the learners and the goals of the community. Programs should assess how participants apply their new knowledge, whether through improved workflows, shared learning, or broader community engagement. ECHOES and, by extension, the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage should encourage the creation of professional networks and peer-learning opportunities to foster collaboration and collective growth. By centring training on people, institutions can ensure that their capacity-building efforts resonate on a human level, driving both personal and professional development.

4.2 Principle 2: Strive for Excellence

High-quality training is central to capacity building. ECHOES underscores the need for rigorous quality assurance mechanisms to uphold the integrity and effectiveness of training content for the heritage sector. Trainers must have expertise in technical matters, practical applications, pedagogical principles, ethics, and values to effectively operate and transfer knowledge in a digital environment. The principle of excellence is not only about disseminating knowledge but also about recognising and validating the achievements of learners, fostering a sense of accomplishment and motivation. Wherever possible, offering formal recognition through microcredentials, ECTS credits, or other certifications validates the learners' efforts and motivates further engagement. This dual focus on quality and recognition ensures that capacity-building initiatives meet the highest standards and provide tangible benefits to participants.

4.3 Principle 3: Foster Openness and Accessibility

To democratise learning, ECHOES emphasises the importance of fostering openness and accessibility. Training resources should be FAIR-by-design (Filiposka et al. 2023). Open licensing should be prioritised to make training materials freely available, promoting widespread access while respecting intellectual property rights. Accessibility goes beyond open licensing; it requires adherence to accessibility standards to ensure content is usable by all, including those with disabilities. By fostering openness and ensuring accessibility, institutions can break down barriers to learning and empower a more inclusive community of CH professionals.

4.4 Principle 4: Promote Inclusion and Diversity

Capacity-building initiatives in ECHOES should actively promote inclusion and diversity to ensure that a wide range of professionals within the cultural heritage (CH) sector can benefit from them. Training activities should be designed to engage a variety of participants, from archivists, curators, and researchers to software developers and policymakers, reflecting the broad spectrum of roles in the sector. Similarly, the training content should cover diverse categories of CH assets (tangible, intangible, digital etc.) in order to ensure relevance across different domains. Training measures should be available in multiple languages and formats to accommodate individuals with varying abilities and backgrounds. Capacity-building efforts should also actively include marginalised and historically disempowered communities to ensure that their unique perspectives and needs are represented and addressed. By embracing inclusivity, institutions can build a more resilient and representative CH workforce.

4.5 Principle 5: Ensure Sustainability

Sustainability is fundamental to any capacity-building effort, as it ensures that training initiatives remain impactful and relevant over time. Training should be seen as an ongoing journey rather than a one-time event. Both learners and providers should commit to life-long learning, continuously updating their knowledge and skills. Establishing a robust maintenance plan is essential for the longevity and effectiveness of training resources. This includes assigning clear roles for oversight and systematically incorporating user feedback. Leveraging tools such as version control systems can facilitate the tracking of updates, streamline the management of changes, and provide transparency to the user community, fostering trust and encouraging ongoing engagement with the resources.

4.6 Principle 6: Provide Flexibility and Adaptability

Flexibility is essential for meeting the diverse needs of learners. Training activities should offer flexible learning pathways, both in terms of duration and formats, allowing participants to choose specific modules or courses without requiring full program completion. This modular approach enables learners to focus on areas most relevant to their roles and career goals. Additionally, training content must be adaptable to different contexts, reflecting linguistic, cultural, national, regional and local nuances. This adaptability ensures that capacity-building efforts are not only effective, fit-for-purpose but also relevant to the specific environments in which they are applied.

4.7 Principle 7: Stay Relevant and Impact-Driven

In a rapidly evolving digital landscape, technology is a moving target. What is cutting-edge today may become obsolete tomorrow. For this reason, providers of training and other capacity-building measures must prioritise staying relevant by continuously updating their content. This involves integrating the latest research, technological advancements, and legal frameworks, such as changes in copyright law, to ensure learners are equipped with current, applicable knowledge. Beyond simply delivering up-to-date information, programs must also be designed with a clear focus on impact. They should help participants develop skills and strategies they can immediately apply in their professional contexts, driving tangible improvements in their work and their organisations. By maintaining relevance and planning for impact, capacity-building initiatives can remain effective, ensuring their long-term value in a constantly shifting environment.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Relation to Other Tasks and Work Packages

The principles described in this deliverable and developed within Subtask 5.2.1 are central to fostering collaboration, enhancing integration, and ensuring the long-term impact of capacity building within the ECHOES project. Together with **T5.2.2** on the **Impact Model**, which will develop a concrete logic and metrics framework for capacity building in ECHOES; and **T5.2.3 Workflows and Processes for Capacity-Building**, which will design efficient methods of operation across the consortium; these principles will directly feed into **T5.2.4**, which will result in a **Strategy and a Roadmap for Training and Knowledge Transfer**.

The capacity-building principles will be considered and shared in the **“Communities” Pillar** and, in particular, **WP4**, whose goal is to **create a new community of professionals, researchers, and users**, sharing with the same concern for the quality and durability of the data available in the Collaborative Cloud. Workshops and events planned under WP4 will play a key role in refining and validating these capacity-building principles. At the time of writing (November 2024), the **identification and mapping of the communities** involved in ECCCH has started with the completion of a questionnaire (distributed by the 16 umbrella institutions partnering with the project through their professional networks at the national and European level), asking professionals about their practices, tools, workflows, needs and expectations regarding both tools and training and a call for volunteers to participate in future workshops.

WP10 has started work on developing **principles for the governance of the Collaborative Cloud**, but these are not yet ready at the time of writing this report. The ambition is to align language between the work packages and make references where possible.

5.2 Paths to Implementation

These Principles for Capacity Building should be embedded into the strategic planning, workflows, and collaborations within the project. In alignment with shared values and goals, consortium members should do their best to ensure that capacity-building goals become a foundational part of their daily operations.

This involves **fostering a learning-centric culture** and developing programs with clear learning outcomes that address the specific needs of their audiences. By offering accessible, modular, and scalable training resources, consortium members can

encourage life-long learning and create opportunities for reflective practices, enabling participants to assess and share how they apply their new skills.

It is recommended that consortium members **adopt a “comply or explain” approach** when applying these principles. If a principle cannot be fully adhered to, an explanation should be provided to clarify the circumstances. For instance, if the accessibility of training is limited — such as being available only through a commercial provider, in a single language, or within a restricted format — this limitation should be justified. An explanation might state that, although the training does not fully align with the principles, it represents the best available option and is preferable to offering no training at all.

Consortium members should **engage diverse stakeholders, including underrepresented communities**, in the design and delivery of their initiatives in order to meet community needs. Employing participatory methods and prioritising equitable access to resources and opportunities can help create a more inclusive environment, ensuring that capacity-building efforts resonate across different groups.

Strengthening partnerships and networks within and beyond the consortium is another effective potential strategy. Consortium members can **co-develop open-access learning resources** and **co-host workshops, webinars, and training sessions** that implement by design these principles. Developing **mentorship programs** and fostering **peer-learning opportunities** can further enhance professional development and leadership within the CH sector. These types of efforts should help establish a **culture of collaboration** and collective growth among stakeholders.

To ensure these efforts have a lasting impact, consortium members should focus on **monitoring and evaluating their capacity-building initiatives**. Establishing metrics to measure success — such as learner satisfaction, skill application, and community impact — allows for continuous refinement and improvement. Gathering feedback from participants and sharing lessons learned across the consortium can inspire best practices and drive innovation.

References

- Corr, Susan, Bosse Lagerqvist, Elis Marçal, Anna Mignosa, and Conor Newman. 2023. 'Mid-Term Results: Matrix and Methodology Assessment'. CHARTER Consortium. <https://charter-alliance.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/D2.3-Mid-term-results-Matrix-and-methodology-assessment-FINAL.pdf>.
- Filiposka, Sonja, Dominique Green, Anastas Mishev, Vojdan Kjorveziroski, Andrea Corleto, Eleonora Napolitano, Gabriella Paolini, et al. 2023. 'D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials'. <https://zenodo.org/records/8305540>.
- Finnis, Jane, and Anra Kennedy. 2022. 'Guide to Digital Transformation in Cultural Heritage'. <https://pro.europeana.eu/project/digital-transformation-task-force>.
- ISCED. 2011. 'International Standard Classification of Education'. <https://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/international-standard-classification-of-education-isced-2011-en.pdf>.
- McNab, Kate. 2021. 'What Do "Digital" and "Digitally Literate Leadership" Mean for My Organisation?' Digital Pathways. 2021. <https://digipathways.co.uk/1-what-do-digital-and-digitally-literate-leadership-mean-for-my-organisation/>.
- Richards, Julian D., Ulf Jakobsson, David Novák, Benjamin Štular, and Holly Wright. 2021. 'Digital Archiving in Archaeology: The State of the Art. Introduction'. Internet Archaeology, no. 58. <https://doi.org/10.11141/ia.58.23>.
- Tasovac, Toma, Sally Chambers, and Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra. 2020. 'Cultural Heritage Data from a Humanities Research Perspective: A DARIAH Position Paper'. <https://hal.science/hal-02961317>.
- UNESCO. 2015. 'Recommendation Concerning the Protection and Promotion of Museums and Collections, Their Diversity and Their Role in Society Adopted by the General Conference at Its 38th Session, Paris, 17 November 2015'. UNESCO Digital Library. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000246331>.